

The Evaluation of the Thermodynamic Parameters of Viscous Flow. Aqueous Solutions of Some Organic Electrolytes

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The thermodynamic parameters of viscous flow, namely : ΔE^* , ΔF^* and ΔS^* at 25° have been calculated for aqueous solutions of four tetraalkyl ammonium bromides and four amino acids, from temperature coefficient data of respectively (i) Kay and coworkers, and England and Pilling, and (ii) Devine and Lowe, together with the apparent molal volume values at 25° reported by Wen and Saito. Nightingale and Benck's equations based on the application of Eyring's theory of absolute reaction rates, have been used. Also, only ΔE^* values at 25° have been calculated from the temperature coefficient data of Tamaki for aqueous solutions of alkyl sulphates, and $\Delta E^* - \Delta E_0^*$ calculated similarly from the data of Rastogi for N-methyl formamide solutions of tetra alkyl ammonium iodides.

EYRING and coworkers¹ have applied the theory of absolute reaction rate to the phenomenon of viscous flow. The energy of activation for viscous flow ΔE^* is found to be given by

$$\Delta E^* = R \frac{d \ln \eta}{d(1/T)} \quad \dots (1)$$

The free energy of activation for viscous flow ΔF^* is given by

$$\Delta F^* = RT \ln \frac{\eta V}{hN} \quad \dots (2)$$

V being the volume of one mole of solution particles, the other symbols having their usual meaning. Nightingale and Benck² have made use of Eyring's idea to interpret the influence of strong electrolytes upon the viscous property of solvents, as summarised in the Jones-Dole equation :

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A \sqrt{C} + BC \quad \dots (3)$$

Neglecting the small \sqrt{C} term which has its origin in interionic attraction³, the Nightingale-Benck equation for activation energy of viscous flow is :

$$\Delta E^* = R \frac{d \ln \eta_0}{d(1/T)} + R \frac{d \ln (1+BC)}{d(1/T)} \quad \dots (4)$$

while the viscous flow free energy is given by the equation already given (equation 2). Assuming further the activation enthalpy to be approximately equal to the activation energy, the expression for entropy of activation is obtained as

$$\Delta S^* = \frac{\Delta E^* - \Delta F^*}{T} \quad \dots (5)$$

Thus, the temperature coefficient of viscosity B-

coefficient of ionic solutions can be made use of to calculate the parameters ΔE^* , ΔF^* , ΔS^* associated with the viscous flow properties of ionic solutions.

Nightingale *et al.*^{2,4} made use of the temperature coefficient data for the viscous flow of solutions of (i) a number of 1-1 and 2-1 electrolytes (Kaminsky⁵, Gurney⁶), and (ii) tetraalkyl ammonium bromides [Nightingale⁴ : tetramethyl ; Laurence and Wolfenden⁷ : tetra-ethyl ; International Critical Tables⁸ : tetrapropyl ; Goldberg and Fuoss⁹ : tetrabutyl] to calculate the values of the associated parameters mentioned. The approach of Nightingale and Benck has been utilised by Japanese workers¹⁰ who have investigated the temperature coefficient of viscous flow of sodium alkyl sulphates and alkyl trimethyl ammonium bromides, and calculated the corresponding parameters.

Kay and coworkers¹¹ have subsequently reported viscosity measurements for tetraalkyl bromides and iodides in H₂O, D₂O, CH₃OH, CH₃CN solutions at various temperatures between 0°-65°. Their data for tetraalkyl ammonium bromide and iodide salts in aqueous solutions have been used by Mandal, Seal and Basu¹² to calculate the corresponding energy of activation only. Devine and Lowe¹³ have reported viscosity measurements for amino acid solutions at different temperatures.

England and Pilling¹⁴ have reinvestigated the temperature coefficient of viscosity B-coefficient, of rather concentrated aqueous solutions of tetraalkyl ammonium bromides.

In view of the current interest in the solvent structure promoting or destroying properties of various solutes as inferred from the study of tem-

perature coefficient of viscous flow, it is imperative to procure and scrutiny critically all information regarding the various parameters associated with such processes. It is the purpose of the present note to present the results of calculation of the parameters ΔE^* , ΔF^* , ΔS^* for four tetraalkyl ammonium bromides and four amino acids, as calculated from temperature coefficient data of viscosity B-coefficient reported respectively by: (i) Kay and coworkers (K)¹¹, and Eagland and Pilling(EP)¹⁴ and (ii) Devine and Lowe¹³.

Calculations and Results

The values of the B-coefficient of four tetraalkyl ammonium bromides have been reported by Kay and coworkers at 10°, 25°, 45° and 65°. Eagland and Pilling¹⁴ have apparently interpolated these data to obtain the values at 15°, 20°, 25°, 30° and 35°; in addition they have reported their own actual measurements at these five temperatures. For comparison, the two sets of B values are shown in Table 1. [Unfortunately, our own interpolation from Kay's results would lead to values somewhat different (generally lower) from those similarly obtained by E. P¹⁴. Moreover, our computerised least square $(\eta/\eta_0 - 1)/\sqrt{C}$ vs. \sqrt{C} plots for those temperatures where such plots are possible from Kay's reported viscosity data 45° and 65° for $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NBr}$; 10°, 45°, 65° for $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{NBr}$; 10°, 25°, 45°, 65° for

$(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_4\text{NBr}$; and 0°, 10°, 25°, 45°, 65° for $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_4\text{NBr}$ lead to yet different B values].

The data for tetramethyl ammonium bromide at 20°, 25°, 30° reported by Nightingale are also shown alongwith.

The $(1+B)$ vs. $1/T$ plots were made on a suitable scale. Besides the plots (over 15°-35° range) from the two sets of tabulated B-T data [(i) EP's, and (ii) Kay's, interpolated by EP], plots have also been made (over 10°-65°) using B values (1) reported by Kay himself; as also (2) computer calculated by us from Kay's viscosity data as mentioned above.

For any particular system out of the four, there is varying degree of agreement between the different plots. For the propyl and butyl salts a nearly parallel run is found (butyl largest positive slope); for the ethyl salt the mutual agreement between EP's and Kay's data is poorest, although Kay's when computerised approach EP's closely. For the methyl salt all plots are moderately close together (EP's interpolation from Kay's data leads to greater scatter), showing an almost parallel run with negative slope. Nightingale's data for this system also show a linear fall, though of much larger negative slope. Nightingale's results, which show

TABLE 1

B-COEFFICIENT DATA OF DIFFERENT WORKERS AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES FOR TETRA ALKYL AMMONIUM BROMIDES

Temp. °C	$(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NBr}$					$(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{NBr}$				$(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_4\text{NBr}$				$(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_4\text{NBr}$				
	a	b	c	d	e	a	b	c	d	a	b	c	d	a	b	c	d	
0°																		1.68 1.67
10°		0.058						0.38	0.414			0.98	1.06					1.46 1.44
15°	0.085	0.075	0.067*			0.398	0.39	0.365*		0.915	0.93	0.92*		1.41	1.41	1.38*		
20°	0.093	0.090	0.076*		0.0627	0.386	0.36	0.352*		0.870	0.870	0.86*		1.36	1.32	1.305*		
25°	0.098	0.083	0.083		0.1014	0.381	0.34	0.34		0.820	0.820	0.820	0.84	1.26	1.24	1.24	1.20	
30°	0.105	0.095	0.088*		0.197	0.368	0.33	0.328*		0.773	0.77	0.758*		1.20	1.18	1.17*		
35°	0.108	0.100	0.092*			0.355	0.32	0.32*		0.733	0.73	0.71*		1.14	1.12	1.10*		
45°		0.10	0.104					0.30	0.341			0.64	0.69				0.99	0.86
65°		0.11	0.118					0.27	0.295			0.54	0.54				0.83	0.82

a.—EP's data¹⁴.

b.—Kay's, interpolated by EP¹⁴,

c.—Kay's own, together with our interpolation(*) from Kay's.

d.—Kay's, computerised by us.

e.—Nightingale's⁴.

* The ΔE^* values calculated from the $(\Delta E + \Delta E^*)$ values reported by Mandal, Seal and Basu¹², who have utilised the same data for the calculation, are quite close (the largest difference is only 5% for the ethyl salt). The slight difference may be attributed to the difference in $(1+B)$ vs. $1/T$ plot; ours were made on suitably large scale and showed up the deviations from linearity.

Also, the η_0 values for water at different temperatures were taken from ref. (15)

very little scatter, appear to be by far the most accurate, in as much as care has been taken to ensure that the intercept A of equation(3) in the $(\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1) / \sqrt{C}$ vs. \sqrt{C} plot agrees with the theoretical estimate of the same. Further, Nightingale's selection of the viscosity data for the other three quarternary salts, and their proper processing (concentration scale correction) is also equally critical.

From the slopes, at 25°, of the tangents to these various (1+B) vs. 1/T plots, the quantities ΔE^* at 25° were calculated according to equation (4), using the value of ΔE_0^* calculated similarly from the slope at 25° of the log η_0 vs. 1/T plot for water*.

$$\Delta E_0^* = R \frac{d \ln \eta_0}{d(1/T)} \quad \dots (6)$$

The ΔE^* values thus calculated from the two sets of data (namely: (1) EP's. and (2) K's, computerised by us) are reported in Table 2, together with the values calculated by Nightingale.**

For the calculation of the free energy of activation of viscous flow at 25° according to equation (2) the viscosity coefficient η and the volume V must be known. The η values are easily calculated by the

Jones-Dole equation (3) (neglecting the \sqrt{C} term), using the reported B-value for the solutions at 25°. The volume (in cc) of one mole of solution particles(V) is given by

$$V = \frac{1000}{n_1 + \nu n_2} \quad \dots (7)$$

where ν is the number of species into which a solute molecule dissociates, and n_2 is the number of moles of solute per liter of solution (molarity of solution). The number of moles of solvent per liter of solution n_1 is given by

$$n_1 = \frac{1000\rho - n_2 M_2}{M_1} \quad \dots (8)$$

where M_1 and M_2 are the molecular weights of the solvent and solute respectively. The densities ρ of the different solutions at 25° (reported only by Eagland *et al* in the microfilm edition of the *J. Phys. Chem.*) have been calculated by using the values of the apparent molal volumes at 25° of the same solutes, as reported by Wen and Saito¹⁶, by means of the expression

$$\phi = \frac{1}{m} \left(\frac{1000 + m M_2}{\rho} - \frac{1000}{\rho_0} \right) \quad \dots (9)$$

TABLE 2
VALUES OF VISCOUS FLOW PARAMETERS FOR TETRAALKYL AMMONIUM BROMIDE AND AMINO ACIDS AT 25°

Solutes	ΔF^* (K cal.s)			ΔE^* (K cal.s.)			ΔS^* (e.u.)		
	a	b		a	b		a	b	
(CH ₃) ₄ NBr	2.295	2.290	2.30 ^c	3.813	3.802	2.85 ^c (2.815)	5.1	5.075	1.85 ^c
(C ₂ H ₅) ₄ NBr	2.463	2.465	2.44 ^d	4.265	4.284	4.11 ^d	6.03	6.029	5.61 ^d
(C ₃ H ₇) ₄ NBr	2.677	2.684	2.75 ^e	4.883	4.976	5.00 ^e	7.4	7.69	7.54 ^e
(C ₄ H ₉) ₄ NBr	2.853	2.836	2.88 ^f	5.072	5.105	6.05 ^f	7.44	7.614	10.6 ^f
Glycine		2.284			3.806			5.11	
Alanine		2.332			3.9272			5.35	
Aminobutyric acid		2.385			4.1106			5.8	
Aminohexanoic acid		2.475			4.4494			6.66	

a.—Eagland and Pilling's data¹⁴

b.—Kay and coworkers data¹¹

c.—Nightingale's data⁴

d, e.—Laurence & Wolfenden's data⁷ and International Critical Table's data⁸ (though only the B values at 25° are reported in ref. 7)

f.—Thermodynamic parameters reported by Nightingale⁴ after calculation from Goldberg and Fuoss's data⁹ using dB/dT values from W.Y. Wen, Ph.D. thesis, Univ. of Pittsburgh, 1957.

* ΔF^* , ΔE^* and ΔS^* for KCl solution calculated from Gurney's B-coefficient data at different temperatures, and density data at 25° from International Critical Tables compilation, agreed exactly with the calculated values of Nightingale, showing the accuracy of our procedure.

** Our calculated ΔE^* value for the methyl salt (from Nightingale's reported temperature coefficient data for B-coefficient of this salt only) is shown alongside Nightingale's own calculated values for this salt, to show the extent of agreement between the two calculations.

'm' being the molality of the solution, and ρ_0 the density of the pure solvent (0.99707 gm/cc). The reported ϕ values of one molal solution at 25° were used.

The calculated η and V values for one molal solution at 25° were used in equation (2) to calculate the corresponding ΔF^* values*. The ΔF^* values thus obtained from the data of the two groups of workers together with Nightingale's calculated values are reported in Table 2.

Finally, assuming the energy and enthalpy of activation to be identical, the ΔS^* values were calculated from the ΔE^* values obtained above, using equation (5). These, obtained from the data of the two groups of workers, together with the values calculated by Nightingale, are also shown in Table 2.

Calculation for amino acid solutions

The viscosity B-coefficient for four different amino acid solutions as obtained from measurements over the concentration range 0.1M to 0.5M, at 15° and 25°, have been reported by Devine and Lowe¹³. From the slopes of the corresponding (1+B) vs. 1/T plots, the ΔE^* values were determined as before. The slope increases steadily from glycine (negative slope) through alanine (slightly negative) and amino butyric acid (positive) to amino hexanoic acid (largest positive). The earlier value for the slope $d \ln \eta_0/d(1/T)$ was used. The density values for one molal solutions at 25° were obtained directly by means of the equation given by these authors, using the reported α and β coefficient values,

$$d = d_0 + \alpha m + \beta m^2$$

Our earlier used ρ_0 value at 25°, which has been

Calculation of ΔE^ for alkyl sulphates in aqueous solutions and ($\Delta E^* - \Delta E_0^*$) for tetraalkyl ammonium iodides in NMF solutions.*

In addition to the data used above, for which complete calculation of all three quantities ΔF^* , ΔE^* , ΔS^* could be carried through, there are data recorded in the literature only for the temperature variation of B-coefficient of some systems, wherefrom ΔE^* can be calculated; however, the density value at none of the working temperatures is recorded, so that ΔF^* and ΔS^* cannot be calculated. Such are the data recorded by Tamaki *et al*¹⁷ for the temperature variation of B-coefficient of some alkyl sulphates in aqueous solution, generally at three different temperatures over the range 10°-50°. The ΔE^* calculation at 25° from the slope of the (1+B) vs. 1/T plot using ΔE_0^* value is straightforward; the results are recorded in Table 3. Rastogi's data¹⁸ for the temperature variation of B-coefficients of tetraalkyl ammonium iodide in N-methyl formamide at 25°, 30° and 35° are interesting in so far as these pertain to non-aqueous solvent; the density values at any temperature being unrecorded, ΔF^* and ΔS^* calculation and their comparison with the corresponding quantities in aqueous solution cannot be carried through. The ΔE^* calculation is again straightforward, and the results are shown in Table 3.

Discussion

From the results presented in columns (c) and (d) of Table 1 it is seen that the very first step in the processing of viscosity data, namely plot of $(\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1)/\sqrt{C}$ vs. \sqrt{C} leads to somewhat different B values according as we consider the result of (i)

TABLE-3 $\Delta E^* - \Delta E_0^*$ FOR TETRAALKYL AMMONIUM IODIDES IN N-METHYL FORMAMIDE AND ΔE^* FOR SODIUM ALKYL SULPHATES IN WATER AT 25°

Alkyl ammonium iodides	$\Delta E^* - \Delta E_0^*(25^\circ)$ (K cal/s)	Sodiumalkyl sulphate (in water)	$\Delta E^* (25^\circ)$ (K cal/s)
Me ₄ NI	-1.338	Methyl sulphate	3.9188
Et ₄ NI	-0.9473	Ethyl sulphate	3.9679
Pr ₄ NI	-0.7539	Propyl sulphate	4.1679
Bu ₄ NI	-0.6987	Pentyl sulphate	5.2400
Pen ₄ NI	-0.5475		
Hex ₄ NI	-0.4882		
Hep ₄ NI	-0.3870		

used here also, is identical with the value used by the authors.

The calculated ΔF^* , ΔE^* , ΔS^* values have been reported in Table 2.

Kay's own plot of his data (column c), and (ii) our computerised least square plot of the same data (in the few cases, enumerated earlier, where this is possible; column d, Table 1). The B values obtained by us are somewhat higher (5-10% generally) than

those reported by Kay, for the methyl, ethyl and propyl salts, while for the butyl salt they are almost same (or, our's even somewhat smaller). However, we do not consider further these results of our processing, because, they are too few in number.

The result of interpolation from the plot of (Kay's) B vs. T , so as to yield the B values at intermediate temperatures not considered by Kay (15° , 20° , 30° , 35°) as reported by Eagland and Pilling (column b), are, surprisingly, different from the result of our interpolation from the same data (column c, data marked*). E.P.'s values are generally higher (most marked for the methyl salt, $\sim 10\%$). (We prefer to consider our interpolation results more reliable, and do not further consider E.P.'s interpolation results). Also, Eagland-Pilling's own data for all the salts at all the five temperatures investigated by them (15 , 20 , 25 , 30 , 35°), are higher than Kay's results [Kay's own, at 25° ; together with our interpolated results (15 , 20 , 30 , 35°) from Kay's wider temperature range (10 , 25 , 45 , 60°) study]. E.P.'s results are ~ 15 - 20% higher for the methyl salt, and ~ 10 - 15% higher for the ethyl salt, while less so for the propyl and butyl salts.

The comparison thus boils down to that between the performance in the further calculations, of the data of Eagland-Pilling, and Kay, as presented respectively in columns (a) and (c) of Table 1. To this must be added the performance of Nightingale's accurate data for the methyl salt (column e). (These B values are significantly different from either the (a) or the (c) column values: $\sim 20\%$ less at 20° , and 35% higher at 30° ; so that the slope of the corresponding $(1+B)$ vs. $1/T$ plot giving the ΔE^* value, is also significantly higher). The thermodynamic parameters calculated from these, shown respectively in columns (a) and (b) of Table 2 for each of the four tetraalkyl salts, and the set marked (c) for the tetramethyl salt only, lead to the following conclusions :

(1) The values of the primary calculated quantities ΔE^* and ΔF^* (and therefore also that of the derived quantity ΔS^*) are not significantly different, as obtained from (i) Eagland-Pilling and (ii) Kay's data (maximum difference: $\sim 4\%$; generally much less). The evaluation of these quantities is thus found to be not significantly sensitive to the processing procedure of the primary viscosity data

$\left(\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1\right) / \sqrt{C}$ vs. \sqrt{C} plot, $(1+B)$ vs. $\frac{1}{T}$ plot, etc.),

provided of course that the processing is reasonably good.

(2) On the other hand, Nightingale's data for the methyl salt leads to significantly smaller ($\sim 30\%$) ΔE^* value for this salt. The ΔF^* value is, however, not significantly altered; so that as a result, the calculated ΔS^* is also markedly ($\sim 6\%$) lower.

(3) The thermodynamic parameters calculated

for the ethyl and propyl salts from Lawrence-Wolfenden's, and the International Critical Tables' results respectively for these salts (sets marked 'd' and 'e' respectively in Table 2) are, however, not markedly different from those calculated from Kay's or E.P.'s data. Only the ΔS^* value for the ethyl salt shows any difference at all ($\sim 6\%$ lower).

(4) Finally, for the butyl salt, the ΔE^* value reported by Nightingale from Goldberg-Fuoss's data, is significantly higher ($\sim 20\%$) than that calculated from E.P.'s or Kay's data. The ΔF^* value is, as before, almost same; so that the calculated ΔS^* value is markedly higher ($\sim 30\%$).

The further discussion of the relative contribution of these calculated enthalpic and entropic changes to the solvent structure-making or structure-breaking characteristics of these quarternary ammonium ions is clearly outside the scope of the present study, which is only restricted rather to the precise determination of the values of these thermodynamic parameters from viscosity measurements, and the critical appraisal of these values when available from different studies. The only significant point to be emphasised in connection with such discussions, as emerges from the present study, is the need for such a critical appraisal; because, as shown above, the magnitudes of both the enthalpic and entropic changes for the same salt as calculated from the results of different investigators, may be markedly different (e.g., for the methyl and butyl salts, above). Consequently, reliable and useful pronouncements regarding the relative importance of these two factors in the process of modification of the solvent structure by the concerned quarternary ammonium cation (or for that matter, any other cation) as revealed by viscosity studies, can only then be made when the values of the associated thermodynamic parameters which form the basis of such discussions, have first been critically appraised.

Unlike the quarternary ammonium salts considered, the values of the thermodynamic parameters for the viscous flow process of the four different amino acids are available from one study only. A slow increase of the entropic change factor with the bulk size of the zwitterion considered, is noteworthy.

Finally, for the tetraalkyl ammonium iodides and the sodium alkyl sulphates, considered in Table 3, the results are obviously incomplete, in so far as in absence of a knowledge of the concomitant $|\Delta F^*$ and ΔS^* values for these organic electrolytes no meaningful discussion regarding the solvent structure promoting or destroying characteristics of these electrolytes can be undertaken. Moreover, for the quarternary ammonium iodides, besides the values of the parameters in the non-aqueous solvent investigated, parallel studies in aqueous solution would lead to the possibility of

illuminating comparative discussions of the dependence of the solvent structure modifying behaviour of any particular quaternary alkyl ammonium ion considered, on the solvent characteristics itself. Very few such comparative studies are recorded in literature.

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